

PROVISIONING AND MANAGING VM'S IN A MULTI-VENDOR PRIVATE CLOUD ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract. There's a lot of focus in delivering multi-vendor private cloud solutions for small and medium business on the market in the world. That stems from the fact that every vendor has something different to offer - VMware is on top in terms of market penetration, Microsoft is making big strides and is a market-leader in terms of presence, RedHat is an upcoming contender that can offer various solutions to the table, and Citrix, whose VDI infrastructure is often present in larger environments. In this paper, we're focusing on making all of them work together for the benefit of the company that owns the infrastructure in private cloud environment.

Introduction

Virtualization and cloud-related technologies seem to be the buzzword in the past couple of years. With its different deployment models – public, private, hybrid – and service models – PaaS, SaaS, IaaS, NaaS – it opened the door to a new era in computing. Different vendors are trying to compete and capture their own part of the market (VMware, Microsoft, RedHat, Citrix), which is also good for the customer as he's faced with choices and excellent levels of competition. This pushes the market forward and brings the prices down - two main business reasons to go with virtualization and cloud technologies in general.

VMware

As the biggest player in the virtualization and cloud market, VMware's vSphere-based technology offers a variety of ways for provisioning and managing its resources. We can start deploying and provisioning virtual machines by using VMware's vSphere Client, which is a standalone solution if you want to connect to vSphere hypervisor directly, without additional costs for licensing vCenter Server or vCenter Server Appliance. Of course, we will lose a lot of functionality by not buying vCenter license as most advanced features (Fault Tolerance, vMotion migrations, VMware High Availability, to name a few) can't work without vCenter Server. And for smaller environments and environments that don't require user-centric provisioning and many other advanced options, this will be enough.

If our basic premise is to provision and manage VMware-based cloud environments, means that we also have to invest in vCloud Director, VMware's star offering for deploying VMware-based clouds. But by getting this product, we're getting access to a variety of tools that will make self-service and VM provisioning an easy task. In translation, if we build on top of vSphere as a hypervisor and vCenter as a service that's going to do the management of our vSphere Hypervisor, we enter the world of vCloud Director, application that will make self-service provisioning possible. After configuring and installing vCloud Director in our environment, we can start using template machines that we created in the vSphere/vCenter environment (or create new ones) and rapidly deploy them with a click of a mouse. We could also use vCloud Automation Center, a high-level application that enables us to do rapid provisioning and managing of cloud services in private and public cloud environments.

All of these applications are the beginning of the VMware story, as VMware's software stack includes many other applications suited to cloud environments - vCenter Orchestrator (workflow-based application that will make fast provisioning of standardized VM's an easy task), vCenter Operations Management Suite (monitoring, compliance, health, risk etc. analyzing application), VMware vCloud Networking and Security (software-based virtual appliance, a networking and security solution that includes firewalling, load balancing, VPN and many other functions), vCenter Site Recovery Manager (virtual appliance with complete disaster recovery and migration solution). Hybrid cloud solutions (integrating private and public clouds) are managed by VMware vCloud Connector, which makes our in-house and public cloud one completely transparent infrastructure. If we want to extend existing functions with additional, custom ones, we have VMware vCloud API at our disposal.

Fig. 1 Overview of VMware's vCloud Suite

If we extend our basic premise to include Microsoft Hyper-V-based cloud environments, then we need to take a closer look at the VMware MHM (Multi-Hypervisor Management), which was introduced in 2012 (version 1.0). The first release included support for Microsoft's Windows Server 2008 R2-based Hyper-V Server. In April 2013., VMware introduced a new version (1.1), that is also able to use the latest Microsoft offering, Server 2012-based Hyper-V Server. With this product, we can easily manage Hyper-V based hosts within the VMware environment, albeit in a limited capacity as all of the features you'd expect to have in such a product aren't yet fully developed.

On a pure deployment and provisioning level, VMware-based solutions offer a lot. We can deploy and provision machines using vSphere Client (entry-level solution), scripting in vCLI (VMware's command line interface), PowerCLI (Microsoft PowerShell-based CLI interface), or vMA (VMware Management Assistant, a virtual appliance that can be used to issue commands to vSphere hypervisors and vCenter hosts from a standardized CLI interface. In terms of guest OS's, VMware's list of supported OS's contains almost all of the Windows versions, many popular Linux distributions and even OS X Server in the last revision. Also, for provisioning of hypervisors, we can use VMware Auto Deploy, that can either physically install our hypervisor from our local network on a new host or load the hypervisor directly into memory of any new host within our environment. This makes it easier to do fast hypervisor upgrades, which we can't do if we're using Microsoft-based solutions. Then, we can use snapshots and templates to deploy additional virtual machines from existing one, and cloning - full or linked - so that we can make exact copies of any virtual machine. If we the same process to the vCloud Director, we can import everything from our vSphere hypervisors, which includes vApps (VMware's way of bundling virtual machines with apps for centralized management and startup/shutdown procedures of provisioned VMs). Then we can clone them, use them as templates, snapshot them, and deploy them as fully self-service provisioned solutions.

Microsoft

While on desktop Microsoft is untouchable, the outlook for Microsoft wasn't as gloomy on the cloud and virtualization part of the market. On the server side, if we count Microsoft Exchange (enterprise e-mail server solution), Microsoft SQL, Sharepoint, Dynamics as a part of the overall strategy, everything looks very good for Microsoft. Windows Server 2008 R2's Hyper-V Server was already a very good virtualization solution before Server 2012 was announced. But the major surprise on a worldwide scale has been the very fast adoption of Windows Server 2012. In terms of virtualization, cloud, networking and storage, Windows Server 2012 is much more suited to cloud environments than Windows Server 2008 R2. The latest version of Hyper-V hypervisor is a standout product in this strategy, and is now on-par with VMware's solutions in terms of features and capabilities. It has also forced VMware to lower prices and remove vRAM entitlements from their licensing model (previously, some VMware products were licensed not by CPU core or socket, but by amount of virtual memory used). Business-wise, this was very welcome for the customers who continue to ask for more and more features for lower and lower price points.

If we deploy a virtualization and cloud solution based on Microsoft's Hyper-V 3.0 (from Windows Server 2012), we will be able to use many advanced features (HA, live migration of VM's and storage, Hyper-V failover clustering, VM replication,) even without going with any additional applications and costs. If we want to do these things on VMware vSphere, we're forced to buy a license for vCenter Server, which is the primary difference in pricing and market strategy between these two industry giants. If we want to automate management and provisioning, resource usage and thresholds, we have to buy Microsoft's System Center.

Microsoft System Center (current version 2012) is a set of application to manage and orchestrate Microsoft-based virtualization and cloud solutions, which can manage VMware-based vSphere environments at the same time. As an application bundle, System Center has Virtual Machine Manager (managing hosts, VM's and Hyper-V clusters), Operations Manager (automation, load balancing, performance and health monitoring), Configuration Manager (compliance and control), Data Protection Manager (data protection and replication solution), Orchestrator (workflow management), App Controller (application management for Microsoft Azure and private clouds), and Service Manager (application for automating best practices like ITIL or MOF).

Fig. 2 Overview of Microsoft's System Center

The major difference between managing and provisioning applications in Microsoft and VMware-based environments is that there are quite a few situations in Microsoft environments where we have to do operations in multiple applications. Workflow management between them is almost non-existent which makes management and maintenance a bit more challenging. VMware's more unified approach might be the better way to go.

From a deployment and provisioning standpoint, we can start with Hyper-V manager on any Windows Server, or with RSAT (Remote System Administration Tools) on any client machine. RSAT is version specific, so if we want to remotely manage Windows Server 2008-gen Hyper-V hosts and VM's from a desktop PC, we will have to use a Windows 7 client. If we want to remotely manage Windows Server 2012-gen Hyper-V hosts and VM's from a desktop PC, we will have to buy a Windows 8-based client. This makes it harder for us to

manage our environment on a basic level. We can use templates, snapshots, export and import functions, single-image type of deployments as means to do provisioning our virtual machines faster.

After that, we can move on to more advanced provisioning and deployment methods, by using WDS (Windows Deployment Services) to install virtual machines, which need to be Windows-based. Linux and other OS's are not directly supported. Self-service provisioning is supported by System Center applications.

RedHat

RedHat's foray into virtualization and cloud world is a fast-evolving topic. Ever since the first version of RHEV (RedHat Enterprise Hypervisor), it was clearly visible that RedHat wants its slice of the market pie, and wants to take a fight to Microsoft and VMware. In RHEV v2.0, RedHat's management platform for virtualization (RHEV-M, RedHat Enterprise Virtualization Manager) was a software application written in .NET that was best suited to a domain-environment with Microsoft SQL Server, and it needed Windows Server 2003 or 2008 R2-based host (or VM). In RHEV 3.x, RHEV-M moved away from Windows Server to RedHat Enterprise Linux as the base OS, to JBoss (RedHat's Java Enterprise Edition platform) and database to Postgres, an open-source database that's free of potentially troubling future of Oracle-owned MySQL. RedHat is still stating that there will be support for Microsoft SQL and Oracle in the future in terms of databases.

Fig. 3 Overview of RedHat Enterprise Virtualization for Servers (same scheme applies to Virtualization for Desktops)

After installing RedHat Enterprise Virtualization Manager, we can use it to deploy virtual machines. Otherwise, we can install VM's by using shell commands, but there's no PowerShell support. Also, RedHat Enterprise Hypervisor is not currently supported as a hypervisor by VMware's Multi-Hypervisor Management or Microsoft's System Center application. This will mean that using RedHat's solution in an environment where we already have Microsoft or VMware-based solutions will mean using additional tools to manage, deploy and provision VM's on RedHat platform. But we can also do self-service deployments for both virtual servers and virtual desktops from the same interface, which is a major difference between RedHat, Microsoft and VMware. Supported Microsoft OS's currently include Windows Server 2003 (32 and 64-bit), 2008 (32 and 64-bit), 2008 R2 and 2012, and - in terms of desktop OS's - Windows XP (32-bit), Windows Vista (32/64-bit), Windows 7 (32/64-bit) and Windows 8 (32/64-bit). In terms of Linux guest support, supported guest OS's include RedHat Enterprise Linux in 3, 4, 5 and 6, both in 32-bit and 64-bit editions. This is a very good solution for private clouds in smaller and medium-size environments as they won't have to buy additional tools to do all of these operations. For enterprise and public clouds, we will have to resort to other solutions, like CloudForms and deltacloud, as these applications will make it easier for us to deliver solutions for RHEV, Amazon's EC2, and even VMware vSphere. Other solution would be to include RHEV support with VMUnify, a suite for managing public, private and hybrid clouds that's almost completely agnostic to the hypervisor it uses as it can support VMware vSphere, Microsoft Hyper-V and Azure, and Amazon EC2.

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I acknowledge that pictures in this paper are taken from marketing materials of VMware, Microsoft and RedHat, and are available on these companies' respective websites. No copyright infringement intended.

Conclusion

The rapid development of virtualization and cloud market poses some new challenges for the market heavyweights. The only way in which the market will have a completely healthy outlook with these technologies is to develop applications that will be able to be completely agnostic to the technology used for clouds (like VMUnify), so that we can consolidate any type of hypervisor under one roof and manage all of our resources from a centralized location.

VMware and Microsoft already made huge strides in this area, as the "multicultural" approach of being able to work with competitor's hypervisor and technology is already available in VMware Multi-Hypervisor Management and Microsoft System Center. There are other products being developed by VMware and Microsoft that will be able to take advantage of other cloud providers and technologies, like Amazon EC2. The end result that everyone is aiming for should be to be able to centrally manage VM's and clouds, and to use all of the necessary operations - fast provisioning, templates, snapshots, clustering, HA solutions - under one roof.

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